

Protocol (V4)

Authors: Cathryn Broderick, Marlene Stewart, Candida Fenton, Sarah Markham, Alex Todhunter-Brown, on behalf of NESSIE

Correspondence to NESSIE, nessie@ed.ac.uk

TITLE

The assessment and management of risk of physical violence toward others posed by adults with a mental health condition in non-forensic health care settings: a scoping review.

Introduction

There is public concern about the risk of harm to others as a result of violence posed by adults with mental health conditions ¹, especially given news coverage of high-profile cases such as the Nottingham attacks (Nottingham Inquiry ²). Although most people with a mental health condition will not be violent towards others in their lifetime ^{3, 4}, there is some evidence that some mental health conditions are associated with a higher risk of violence, resulting in harm to others, compared with people without a mental health condition ⁵⁻⁸. A recent systematic review and meta-analysis reported this risk as less than 1 in 20 in women with schizophrenia spectrum disorders and less than 1 in 4 in men with schizophrenia spectrum disorders over a 35-year period ⁵, and an earlier systematic review reported the risk of violence in people with schizophrenia and other psychoses compared to general population varied between one and seven in men, and between four and 29 in women ⁹. Early interventions in psychosis services have been shown to reduce both hospitalisations and deaths from suicide. Early identification of a need to intervene to prevent harm as a result of mental health conditions will likewise decrease unwanted outcomes such as violence to potential victims (others) and premature mortality in people at risk of causing self-harm ^{6, 10, 11}. Guidelines have been produced for use in forensic healthcare settings which aim to provide clinical guidance on both the assessment and management of risk of harm to others posed by adults with mental health conditions, as well as guidelines on self-harm ^{12, 13}. However, it is unclear how relevant these guidelines are for risk (or threat) of violence toward others posed by adults attending non-forensic healthcare settings ¹⁴. Best practice guidance applicable to non-forensic settings requires updating ^{15, 16}. Furthermore,

the evidence base from published research studies in this area has not previously been collated.

Violence can be defined as a “behaviour involving physical force intended to hurt, injure or kill”¹⁷. However, often definitions of violence can include sexual violence or assault (e.g. Youn 2025⁸). To make a clear distinction, we use the phrase interpersonal physical violence. We define interpersonal physical violence as a behaviour involving actual physical force resulting in injury to, or even death of, another person. Behaviours can include a range of physical acts, including physical abuse and assault and assault using a weapon (including with knives or guns). We define abuse as physical cruelty or violence towards another person and assault as a physical attack on another person. We define a risk or threat as an intention or likelihood to inflict physical violence on another person.

A number of patient characteristics and other risk factors are thought, and at least partially evidenced, to be associated with an increased risk of interpersonal physical violence. These include (amongst others) schizophrenia spectrum disorders, presence of substance misuse, previous violence perpetration and victimization^{15,18}. Early treatment interventions for these risk factors may therefore impact on potential risk of interpersonal physical violence¹⁹. Risk prediction remains difficult because episodes of violent behaviour remain rare, risk assessment is specific to the current situation and cannot predict a specific outcome¹. Barriers reported to assessment and management include concern over reinforcing stigma and subsequent reduced engagement in treatment^{4,15}. Social and health inequalities around race have been shown to impact on how different ethnicities access mental health services, with more people from non-white ethnic backgrounds having forensic services as first contact^{20,21}. A number of tools (incorporating such risk factors) have been developed for use, primarily in forensic settings²²⁻²⁵, with one metareview identifying as many as 120 different risk assessment tools (internationally and locally implemented) being used in forensic (psychiatric) and general settings²⁶. However, it is not certain which tools, if any, are the best to use in a non-forensic setting, nor indeed whether they are helpful when compared with more nuanced clinical assessment approaches^{24,27,28}. There is also variation in how risk of interpersonal physical violence is assessed across the UK¹.

Management of risk of interpersonal physical violence in the forensic setting traditionally considers both management of the individual with the mental health condition (e.g. via personalised management plans and treatment of both the presenting mental health condition and co-morbidities) and consideration of carers/family^{12,15,16}. Again, the evidence base on best management approaches from research studies specifically in non-forensic patient populations has not previously been collated in a way which is helpful for the development of clinical guidance. To enable development of meaningful guidance on assessment and management of risk of interpersonal physical violence for general mental health services, there is an urgent need to collate all relevant research to allow an accurate overview of the current evidence base.

AIM / objective

Our aim is to identify research literature which can inform the development of clinical guidelines on the assessment and management of risk of interpersonal physical violence posed by adults with mental health conditions in non-forensic healthcare settings. The

guidelines are aimed at (i) assessing, clinically, the risk such adults pose of interpersonal physical violence both in the healthcare setting and external to that setting, and (ii) managing the risk of physical violence to others. A second evidence synthesis is proposed to look at the same issues in children and adolescents.

Research questions

What is the volume (number of studies and number of participants) and key characteristics of evidence on the following topics and sub-topics?

1. Assessment of risk of interpersonal physical violence by adults with a mental health condition in non-forensic mental healthcare settings, including:
 - a) Use of any tool(s) to assess risk of interpersonal physical violence
 - b) Accuracy/validity of named tool(s)
 - c) Use of methods/approaches other than a tool to assess risk of interpersonal physical violence (including individual risk factors)
 - d) Use of a tool combined with other approaches to assess risk of interpersonal physical violence
 - e) Identification of factors (individual or institutional or societal) which increase the risk of interpersonal physical violence
 - f) Identification of factors (individual or institutional or societal) which reduce the risk of interpersonal physical violence

2. Management of risk of interpersonal physical violence by adults with a mental health condition in non-forensic mental health care settings, including:
 - a) Treatment of mental health condition, co-morbidities, substance misuse
 - b) Psychological therapies which may reduce risk of violence, e.g. cognitive behavioural therapy, behavioural therapies, anger/aggression focussed therapy
 - c) Supervision/monitoring/system structures, e.g. case-workers, supported housing, observation activities
 - d) Family/carer related interventions
 - e) Victim safety planning

Research questions are designed to map to the likely sub-sections of the final guidelines.

METHODS

Design

We will conduct a systematic scoping review. Scoping reviews provide a systematic method to identify and to provide an overview or map of key literature, often around a broad topic. They commonly explore the volume and key characteristics of evidence, making this an appropriate methodology to address our research questions^{29 30, 31}. We will follow guidance from the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI)³⁰ and report our findings according to the PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR)³¹.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

a) Relevant study/article types

The scoping review will include:

- (i) Systematic reviews. We define a 'systematic review' as: a research process in which literature relevant to a stated question is identified and brought together (synthesised) using explicit methods ³², including reporting of inclusion/exclusion criteria, search methods and details of included studies. We will include systematic reviews regardless of the type of evidence synthesised (i.e. quantitative, qualitative, mixed-methods) and the type of question addressed (e.g. epidemiology, intervention effectiveness, diagnostic test accuracy, qualitative experiences).
- (ii) Primary research studies. This will include both quantitative and qualitative research studies, including, but not limited to, clinical trials, observational epidemiological studies - prospective, cross-sectional, case control - service evaluation, DTA/tool development/validation studies, risk prediction studies, qualitative studies). We will exclude single case-studies, case-series with <10 participants, policy statements, narrative commentaries/reviews and similar documents. We will exclude studies that are published as an abstract only, as these are considered unlikely to contain sufficient information to inform guideline development. We will exclude study protocols or descriptions of ongoing studies (e.g. clinical trial records), but will search for, maintain and report a list of these, as these may be relevant to future updates of this evidence base.

b) Population

The study population will be adults with mental health conditions receiving care from a non-forensic mental health care setting (see below for definitions). We will include adults of 18 years or older. This includes elderly, veterans, and men and women. We will exclude children and adolescents aged less than 18 years. These will be considered in a second scoping review.

The study population must be in non-forensic mental health care settings; this includes adults receiving care from a mental health service or team or autism service or team. This includes (but is not limited to) adults living in community settings and receiving care from primary care / community mental health services, general psychiatric services, specialist mental health services (including autism services) and adults who are inpatients within general psychiatric hospital settings. The setting refers to the health care setting within which patients are receiving care, not necessarily the setting where there is a risk of violence being committed.

NHS national codes for describing mental health services ³³ within the UK are provided in Appendix 1, with a note of services considered relevant to this review. However, terms and descriptions used for mental health services are anticipated to differ in other countries.

We will exclude:

- Populations receiving care from (or known to) forensic mental health services, including forensic learning disability services. Forensic mental health services provide specialist evidence-based treatment and care for individuals with mental health

conditions who have offended, are at risk of offending, or are otherwise at high risk of causing harm to others. These services are provided in inpatient settings and in the community, and include high, medium and low secure inpatient services and community forensic services.

- Populations receiving care from specialist teams focussed on paediatrics, young people, eating disorders, acquired brain injury or learning disabilities (other than autism or attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD)).
- Populations receiving care from services relating to prison or justice services.

If studies include participants from a mix of eligible and ineligible settings, or it is unclear whether a study is confined exclusively to patients in eligible settings (as defined above), these papers will be included in the scoping review and identified as either 'unclear setting' or 'mixed setting'. A list of studies excluded because they are based within forensic mental health service settings only will be maintained and reported. This is because it is acknowledged that, in practice, final guidance may be extrapolated from research in a forensic setting where this is lacking for the non-forensic setting.

c) Concept

We are interested in assessment and/or management of risk/threats of or actual inter-personal physical violence. As previously stated, definitions are:

Interpersonal physical violence: a behaviour involving actual physical force resulting in injury to, or even death of, another person. Behaviours can include a range of physical acts, including physical abuse and assault and assault using a weapon (including with knives or guns). We define abuse as physical cruelty or violence towards another person and assault as a physical attack on another person.

Risk/threat: an intention or likelihood to inflict physical violence on another person.

We will exclude studies focussed on sexual or psychological violence, abuse or assault.

Assessment and/or management of risk/threat: We will include research studies that explore:

- Development, testing and use of assessment tools to identify those at risk of inter-personal physical violence
- Identification of factors that may predict, or be associated with, increased or decreased risk of inter-personal physical violence
- Management strategies or treatments designed to reduce risk of inter-personal physical violence

We will exclude studies focussed on development and testing of assessment tools that are primarily designed for use in forensic healthcare or wider prison setting, unless these are explicitly being used or tested in non-forensic settings.

We will exclude studies focused on development of assessment tools where (i) the tool is not specifically focussed on assessment of risk of violence, excluding tools which have one or two single violence-related items as part of a broader assessment, and (ii) the tool is not specifically designed for people with mental health conditions, excluding studies developing tools to assess risk of violence in the general population. If studies test a (general) tool for

assessment of risk of violence on a population with mental health problems, these would be included.

d) Context

Geographical scope. We will only include studies undertaken in populations residing in high-income countries (according to the World Bank ³⁴), including UK, Australia, New Zealand, Canada, USA and European countries.

Searching and screening

Approach: The topic for this scoping review is broad and the searching and screening anticipated to be complex. Following JBI guidance that highlights the value of iterative development of searches and the importance of balancing comprehensiveness with available times and resources ³⁰, we plan a two-stage approach:

- Stage 1: Systematic reviews. We will first search for and identify systematic reviews which meet our inclusion criteria. The benefits of this are twofold. Firstly, high-quality systematic reviews will potentially provide best evidence for the development of a guideline. Although not standard in scoping reviews, we will assess the quality of relevant systematic reviews. Secondly, there are validated search filters for systematic reviews enabling a manageable search which can help inform the development of the search for primary studies.
- Stage 2: Primary studies. Following the completion of Stage 1 searching and screening, we will conduct a search for primary studies. The Stage 2 search strategy will be informed by the findings from stage 1.

For both Stage 1 and Stage 2 searches we will follow the Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies (PRESS) for systematic reviews guidance ³⁵.

Search strategy: Due to the complexity of the search required for this scoping review, and the need to pragmatically balance the anticipated large volume of search results with the available resources, a complete search strategy is not included within this protocol. Search strategies for Stage 1 and Stage 2 will be designed by an information specialist, in consultation with people with specialist topic expertise, and peer-reviewed according to PRESS guidance. We will transparently report the final search strategies, and key steps and decisions in the iterative development of this.

Databases: we will search the following databases:

- the Cochrane Library
- Medline via Ovid
- Embase via Ovid
- CINAHL via Ebsco
- PsycInfo via Ovid

For Stage 2 in addition to the databases above, we will search the following trial registries:

- ICTRP
- ClinicalTrials.gov

This is to ensure that information on research being undertaken will also be retrieved.

Search time period: For Stage 1, we will search for systematic reviews published in the last 10 years (i.e. from January 2016 onwards). There has been a large change in societal influences on mental health presentation and management over the past 5-10 years, and systematic reviews published before January 2016 are considered unlikely to contain evidence that is directly relevant to the proposed guideline. The search time period for Stage 2 will be informed by the findings of Stage 1 but is anticipated to be no greater than 5 years. Focussing on no more than 5 years will ensure identification of recent publications that are most likely to be directly relevant to the proposed guideline.

Language: We will only include studies published in English. This is due to the limited time and resources available for this scoping review, meaning we are unable to retrieve and translate studies published in languages other than English.

Management of searching and screening: Results of the searches will be de-duplicated in EndNote Version 20.3, 2020 (Clarivate Analytics, PA, USA) and uploaded into Covidence³⁶. One reviewer will pre-screen the search results to exclude any clearly irrelevant studies. Two reviewers will then independently apply inclusion criteria to titles and abstracts, deciding if each is an ‘exclude’ or ‘potential include’. Any studies where there are disagreements between the independent reviewers will be discussed to reach consensus on a decision, involving a third reviewer if necessary.

Full texts will be obtained for all studies considered as ‘potential includes’. Two reviewers will independently apply inclusion criteria, and reach consensus through discussion, involving a third reviewer, if necessary, where there are disagreements. All full-text papers selected as ‘include’ at this stage will be included in the review. We will include at the study level (i.e. if there are multiple papers reporting the same study, we will group these together and count as a single study).

Reasons for exclusion will be documented as one of:

- For Stage 1: 1. Publication not in English; 2. Abstract only; 3. Ongoing study / protocol; 4. Wrong study design (not a systematic review); 5. Search date 2015 or earlier; 6. Wrong concept (i.e. not focussed on interpersonal physical violence); 7. Wrong patient population (i.e. not adults); 8. Wrong patient population (i.e. not diagnosed with a mental health condition, or not attending mental health care services); 9. Wrong setting (i.e. study primarily focussed on forensic setting); 10. Focussed on LMIC studies only; 11. Other.
- For Stage 2: 1. Publication not in English; 2. Abstract only; 3. Ongoing study / protocol; 4. Study not conducted in a high-income country; 5. Wrong study design (i.e. not a primary study, single/small case reports); 6. Wrong concept (i.e. not focussed on interpersonal physical violence); 7. Wrong patient population (i.e. not

adults); 8. Wrong patient population (i.e. not diagnosed with a mental health condition, or not attending mental health care services); 9. Wrong setting (i.e. study primarily focussed on forensic setting); 10. Evaluation (accuracy/validity) of risk assessment tools used in forensic settings; 11. Other.

Where there are multiple reasons for exclusion, we will adopt a hierarchical approach, selecting the first appropriate reason for exclusion from the list above. Where reviewers are uncertain (i.e. cannot reach consensus through discussion between reviews) about whether a study does or does not meet the inclusion criteria, key interest-holders will be consulted and these views used to inform research team decisions.

The results of the searches will be reported, including a PRISMA flow chart³¹ which clearly details the decision processes at each stage of the process.

Data extraction and coding

Within Covidence, two reviewers will independently extract/code the following data from included studies, with disagreements resolved through discussion:

Stage 1 (systematic reviews)

- Author, year
- Aim – verbatim text
- Aim: Categorisation of whether systematic review synthesises evidence relating to:
 - Assessment of risk of physical violence (tools), with verbatim extraction of name of tool explored
 - Factors associated with increased/decreased risk of physical violence (risk factors), with verbatim extraction of risk factors explored
 - Management or treatment, with verbatim extraction of management strategy / approach / intervention, and additional codes as to whether the focus is:
 - treatment of mental health condition
 - psychological therapies to reduce risk
 - supervision / monitoring/ system structure
 - Families / carers
 - Focus is on victim safety planning
 - Other
- Total number of included studies (and the number focussed on adults with a mental health condition seen in a non-forensic health care setting where a review includes mixed populations)
- Total number of participants within included studies
- Mental health setting focussed on by systematic review (verbatim text)
- Mental health condition focussed on by systematic review (verbatim text)
- Definition of physical violence (verbatim text)
- Demographic characteristics. Is information included about the characteristics of participants within the studies included in the review (yes/no/unclear):
 - Age

- Gender/sex
- Race/ethnicity
- History of physical violence
- Mental health conditions
- Categorisation of whether systematic review synthesises evidence relating to:
 - Non-forensic mental health services
 - Mixed forensic and non-forensic health services
 - Unclear setting

Stage 2 (primary studies)

- Author, year
- Country study was conducted
- Aim – verbatim text
- Aim – coded as aims that are focussed on synthesising evidence relevant to:
 - development, testing and use of assessment tools
 - identification of risk factors
 - Management strategies and interventions
 - Other
- Study design – coded as:
 - Intervention study
 - Randomised trial
 - Non-randomised intervention studies (includes non-randomised trial, controlled before & after study, interrupted time series study, repeated measures study) ³⁷
 - Observational study (includes cohort study, cross-sectional study, case-control study, survey, case-series (≥ 10 participants))
 - Qualitative and mixed methods studies (includes studies with interviews, focus groups etc)
 - Diagnostic test accuracy/tool development/validation studies
 - Other (e.g. service evaluation, economic evaluation, modelling studies)
- Population – age - coded as (selecting all that apply):
 - Adults
 - Older adults (> 65 years)
 - Veterans
 - Other
- Population – history of violence – coded as, participants have:
 - Previous history of physical violence
 - No history of physical violence
 - Mixed group including participants with and without history of violence
 - No information on history of violence presented
- Sample size – total number of participants (the number focussed on adults with a mental health condition seen in a non-forensic health care setting where a review includes mixed populations))
- Demographic characteristics. Are any study results presented separately according to different:

- Gender/sex (relevant subgroup results reported; limited subgroup analyses presented; baseline characteristics reported only; no information)
- Race/ethnicity (relevant subgroup results reported; limited subgroup analyses presented; baseline characteristics reported only; no information)
- Mental health condition(s) of participants within included studies (coded according to relevant ICD-11 diagnoses, see Appendix 2):
 - Schizophrenia or other primary psychotic disorders
 - Mood disorders
 - Substance-induced mood or psychotic disorders
 - Disorders specifically associated with stress
 - Dissociative disorders
 - Impulse control disorders
 - Disruptive behaviour or dissocial disorders
 - Personality disorders and related traits
 - Neurodevelopmental disorders: Autism spectrum disorders
 - Neurodevelopmental disorders: Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder
 - Other
 - Unspecified
- Mental health setting from which participants are recruited: verbatim text
- Place of residence of participants (at recruitment):
 - Community / home setting (with or without family/carers)
 - Supported housing or supported living services ³⁸
 - In-patient hospital setting
 - Other
- Mental health services attended by participants:
 - Non-forensic mental health services
 - Mixed forensic and non-forensic health services
 - Unclear setting

In addition:

- For studies categorised as focussed on assessment of risk of violence, we will extract:
 - Name of assessment tool (if relevant)
 - Name or brief description of methods / approach other than a tool (if relevant)
 - Are there data relating to the use of the tool? (Y / N / U)
 - Are there data relating to accuracy / validity of tool (Y / N / U)
- For studies categorised as focussed on factors associated with increased/decreased risk of physical violence, we will extract:
 - Risk factor(s)
 - Method of measurement of physical violence (e.g. assessment tool)
 - Does the study provide statistical data demonstrating association between factor and risk of physical violence? (Y / N / U)
- For studies categorised as focussed on management or treatment, we will extract:
 - Name of management strategy / approach / intervention
 - And we will code whether the focus is on:
 - treatment of mental health condition
 - psychological therapies to reduce risk

- supervision / monitoring/ system structure
- families / carers
- focus is on victim safety planning

This additional coding will be discussed with key interest-holders on a regular basis, with further codes introduced if required.

Piloting: We will pilot our data extraction form with at least 10 included studies. We will discuss the results of the pilot coding and refine accordingly. We will document any revisions to categories and justification for these.

Quality assessment of included studies

Stage 1 - Systematic reviews: We will assess the risk of bias of any included systematic reviews using AMSTAR 2 (a critical appraisal tool for systematic reviews)³⁹. Our justification for this is that knowledge of the quality of systematic reviews will be central to informing decisions about relevance of systematic review findings to the proposed guideline. Two independent reviewers will make AMSTAR judgements, with disagreements resolved through discussion. Within our evidence synthesis, we will note that the AMSTAR tool provides a judgement of the quality of methods of the systematic review, and not the studies included within the systematic review.

Stage 2 - Primary research: We will not assess risk of bias of primary research studies. Rationale for this is that scoping review often do not involve conducting quality appraisals of studies, as the main purpose of a scoping review is to describe a body of literature by characteristics and factors as outlined in the aims and research questions of the review⁴⁰. To optimise efficiency, assessment of risk of bias of studies considered relevant to the guideline should be conducted during the guideline development process. Information within this scoping review relating to study design, study size, study focus and participant details will inform decisions about potential relevance of individual studies to the proposed guideline⁴¹.

DATA SYNTHESIS AND PRESENTATION

We will present the results in the form of tables.

Included studies will be categorised according to the specific research questions for this scoping review which have been designed to map to the sub-sections of the proposed guidelines. This will be done to provide an evidence-base which can be easily accessed by experts in the field when they come to writing each guideline section. Depending on the volume of literature identified, it may be desirable to list individual studies within tables.

We anticipate that this will include:

- i. An overview of included studies (see Dummy tables 1a and 1b)
- ii. An overview of participants included within the studies (see Dummy table 2)
- iii. A summary of evidence relating to each research question / topic:
 - Summary of studies focussed on assessment of risk of physical violence (Dummy table 3)

- Summary of studies focussed on identification of factors associated with increased/decreased risk of physical violence (Dummy table 4)
- Summary of studies focussed on management of people at risk of physical violence (Dummy table 5)

However, if a high volume of literature for any research question/subsection is found, summary tables displaying volumes of studies may be considered useful. Final decisions on presentation of data within tables will be taken in discussion with the commissioning interest-holders.

Dummy table 1a: Overview of included systematic reviews

Review name and date	Review aim (verbatim quote)	Review focus (categorised as: Assessment tools; Risk factors; Management; Other)	Mental health setting on which review focusses (verbatim quote)	Number of included studies	Number of participants	Review quality (AMSTAR assessment)		
Study 1								
Study 2								
Study 3								etc

Dummy table 1b: Overview of included primary studies

Study name and data	Study aim (verbatim quote)	Study focus (categorised as: Assessment tools; Risk factors; Management; Other)	Study design	Country	Number of participants	Mental health setting from which participants are required (verbatim quote)		
Study 1								
Study 2								
Study 3								etc

Dummy table 2: Overview of participants included in included primary studies

Study name	Age	Mental health condition included in study (tick all that apply)								Included participants have	Information relating to		
		Schizophrenia or other primary psychotic disorders	Mood disorders	Substance-induced mood or psychotic disorders	Personality disorders	Disorders specifically associated with	Neurodevelopmental disorders	Other	Unspecified		Previous history of physical violence (Y / N / U)	Place of residence	Gender / sex
Study 1													

Study 2													
Study 3													

Dummy table 3: Summary of studies focussed on assessment of risk of physical violence

Study	Study design (review or primary study)	Study aim (verbatim quote)	Name of assessment tool (if relevant)	Method / approach other than a tool (if relevant)	Does the study contain data relating to use of tool / method / approach to assessment? (Y / N / U)	Does the study contain data relating to accuracy / validity of tool / method / approach to assessment? (Y / N / U)	Key notes
Study 1							
Study 2							
Study 3							

Dummy table 4: Summary of studies focussed on identification of factors associated with increased/decreased risk of physical violence

Study	Study design (review or primary study)	Study aim (verbatim quote)	Name of factor(s) investigated	Method of assessing risk of physical violence (e.g. name of tool)	Does the study provide statistical data demonstrating association between factor and risk of physical violence? (Y / N / U)	Key notes
Study 1						
Study 2						
Study 3						

Dummy table 5: Summary of studies focussed on management of people at risk of physical violence

Study	Study aim (verbatim quote)	Study design (review or primary study)	Study size (number of participants)	Name of management strategy / approach / intervention	Focus is on treatment of mental health condition	Focus is on psychological therapies to reduce risk (Y / N / U)	Focus is on supervision / monitoring / system structure (Y / N / U)	Focus is on victim safety planning (Y / N / U)	Key notes

					n (Y / N / U)				
Study 1									
Study 2									
Study 3									

We will write a brief narrative synthesis summarising the volume (number and size of studies) and key characteristics (e.g. study design, country, population) of the research evidence according to the research questions and sub-questions that have been identified. We will highlight questions and sub-questions that have been addressed by systematic reviews and briefly comment on the volume and quality of evidence. The synthesis will provide a commentary on the characteristics of the people included in the studies. This commentary will not bring together the results of the identified studies.

TEAM REFLEXIVITY / POSITIONALITY STATEMENT

To enhance transparency, our narrative synthesis will include a team reflexivity statement summarising the different goals of the researchers working on the evidence map. We will employ the definition of reflexivity as “a set of continuous, collaborative, and multi-faceted practices through which researchers self-consciously critique, appraise, and evaluate how their subjectivity and context influence the research processes”⁴².

DISSEMINATION / KNOWLEDGE MOBILISATION

We will develop and maintain a knowledge mobilisation plan. We will discuss this with our commissioning interest-holders and refine iteratively through the course of the project. A key aim of this plan will be to engage with and communicate the findings of this scoping review with key experts from NHSE.

We will work with our interest-holders to explore how we can support wider knowledge mobilisation and measure longer-term impact.

INTEREST-HOLDER ENGAGEMENT

A NESSIE PPI co-investigator will oversee the interest-holder involvement in this review. We will follow national standards and principles⁴³⁻⁴⁵. We aim to engage with clinical experts from NHSE throughout, ideally recruiting people with relevant adult mental health care experience, including nursing, psychiatry, psychology, occupational therapy and social work experience. We will explore, with clinical experts, opportunities to engage people with lived experience (i.e. patients, family members, public) at the phase of data synthesis and dissemination, with a focus on ensuring clear presentation of results. We will report the involvement of interest-holders using the ACTIVE framework and GRIPP2 reporting checklist (short form)^{46, 47}

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For the purpose of open access, the author has applied a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) licence to any Author Accepted Manuscript version arising from this submission.

CONTRIBUTIONS OF AUTHORS

Please see Appendix 3 for the CRediT author statement.

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APPENDIX 1: NHS national codes for mental health service or team

From these codes we would include:

- Populations receiving care from mental health service or teams with assigned codes of A01-A25.
- Populations receiving care from autism services (NHS national code C01). An autism service is defined as a service which “provides diagnosis, treatment and signposting for patients with a diagnosis or seeking a diagnosis of autism” (NHS ⁴⁸).

We will exclude:

- Populations receiving care from (or known to) forensic mental health services (NHS national code B01) or forensic learning disability services (NHS national code B02). For the purposes of this scoping review, a forensic mental health service is defined as a service which provides specialist evidence-based treatment and care for individuals with mental health conditions who have offended, are at risk of offending, or are otherwise at high risk of causing harm to others. These services are provided in inpatient settings and in the community, and include high, medium and low secure inpatient services and community forensic services.
- Populations receiving care from specialist teams focussed on paediatrics, young people, eating disorders, acquired brain injury or learning disabilities (NHS national codes C02-C10, E01-E04).
- Populations receiving care from services relating to prison or justice services (NHS national codes D02-D03)

Code	Description
A01	Day Care Service
A02	Crisis Resolution Team/Home Treatment Service
A03	Crisis Resolution Team (Retired 1 October 2021)
A04	Home Treatment Service (Retired 1 October 2021)
A05	Primary Care Mental Health Service
A06	Community Mental Health Team - Functional
A07	Community Mental Health Team - Organic
A08	Assertive Outreach Team
A09	Community Rehabilitation Service

A10	General Psychiatry Service
A11	Psychiatric Liaison Service
A12	Psychotherapy Service
A13	Psychological Therapy Service (non IAPT)
A14	Early Intervention Team for Psychosis
A15	Young Onset Dementia Team
A16	Personality Disorder Service
A17	Memory Services/Clinic/Drop in service
A18	Single Point of Access Service
A19	24/7 Crisis Response Line
A20	Health Based Place of Safety Service
A21	Crisis Café/Safe Haven/Sanctuary Service
A22	Walk-in Crisis Assessment Unit Service
A23	Psychiatric Decision Unit Service
A24	Acute Day Service
A25	Crisis House Service
B01	Forensic Mental Health Service
B02	Forensic Learning Disability Service
C01	Autism Service
C02	Specialist Perinatal Mental Health Community Service

C03	Eating Disorders/Dietetics Service (Retired 1 April 2020)
C04	Neurodevelopment Team
C05	Paediatric Liaison Service
C06	Looked After Children Service
C07	Youth Offending Service
C08	Acquired Brain Injury Service
C09	Community Eating Disorder Service (CEDS) for Children and Young People (Retired 1 April 2020)
C10	Community Eating Disorder Service
D01	Substance Misuse Team
D02	Criminal Justice Liaison and Diversion Service
D03	Prison Psychiatric Inreach Service
D04	Asylum Service
D05	Individual Placement and Support Service
D06	Mental Health In Education Service
D07	Problem Gambling Service
D08	Rough Sleeping Service
E01	Community Team for Learning Disabilities
E02	Epilepsy/Neurological Service
E03	Specialist Parenting Service
E04	Enhanced/Intensive Support Service

F01	Education-based Mental Health Support Team
F02	Maternal Mental Health Service
F03	Mental Health Services for deaf people
F04	Veterans Complex Treatment Service (Retired 1 April 2024)
F05	Enhanced care in Care Homes teams
F06	Mental Health and Wellbeing Hubs
F07	Armed Forces Veterans Integrated Treatment Service
Z01	Other Mental Health Service - in scope of National Tariff Payment System
Z02	Other Mental Health Service - out of scope of National Tariff Payment System

APPENDIX 2: Mental health conditions (ICD-10 and ICD-11)

Mental health conditions

We will categorise study populations according to diagnosed mental health condition(s). Relevant diagnoses according to the International Classification of Diseases ICD-10⁴⁹ or ICD-11⁵⁰ include:

ICD-10 diagnoses⁴⁹:

- Mental and behavioural disorders due to psychoactive substance use (ICD-10, F10-F19) (includes alcohol and drug use)*
- Schizophrenia, schizotypal and delusional disorders (ICD-10, F20-F29)
- Mood (affective) disorders (ICD-10, F30-39)
- Neurotic and stress-related disorders:
 - Anxiety disorders (other) (ICD-10, F41)
 - Obsessive-compulsive disorder (ICD-10, F42)
 - Reaction to severe stress, and adjustment disorders (ICD-10, F43)
 - Dissociative disorders (ICD-10, F44)
 - Neurotic disorders (other) (ICD-10, F48)
- Disorders of adult personality and behaviours (ICD-10, F60-69)
- Pervasive developmental disorders (ICD-10, F84)

*Those with (only) a diagnosis of acute drug or alcohol intoxication (ICD-10, F10.0, F11.0, F12.0, F13.0, F14.0, F15.0, F16.0, F17.0, F18.0 or F19.0) will be excluded.

ICD-11 diagnoses⁵⁰:

- Neurodevelopmental disorders
 - Autism spectrum disorder (6A02)
 - Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (6A05)
- Schizophrenia or other primary psychotic disorders (6A20-6A25)
- Mood disorders
 - Bipolar or related disorders (6A60-6A63)
 - Depressive disorders (6A70-6A73)
- Substance-induced mood or psychotic disorders (6C40-6C49)
- Disorders specifically associated with stress (6B40-6B45)
- Dissociative disorders (6B60-6B66)
- Impulse control disorders (6C70-6C73)
- Disruptive behaviour or dissocial disorders (6C90-6C91)
- Personality disorders and related traits (6D10, 6D11)

APPENDIX 3: CRediT author statement

Term	Definition	Contributors
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	ATB, JP, CB, MS, CF
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	ATB, JP, CB, MS, CF
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components; designing of search strategies	CF
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs	n/a
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyse or synthesize study data	n/a
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	n/a
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	n/a
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	CB, MS
Writing - Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	CB, MS, ATB, CF
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre-or postpublication stages	CB, MS, ATB, CF, SM
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation	n/a
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team	ATB, CB, MS

Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution	MS, CB, ATB
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication	n/a

APPENDIX 4: Reporting checklist for this protocol

We have used the checklist for Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR):

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a scoping review.	1
ABSTRACT			
Structured summary	2	Provide a structured summary that includes (as applicable): background, objectives, eligibility criteria, sources of evidence, charting methods, results, and conclusions that relate to the review questions and objectives.	Not applicable (this is a protocol)
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known. Explain why the review questions/objectives lend themselves to a scoping review approach.	1-2
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the questions and objectives being addressed with reference to their key elements (e.g., population or participants, concepts, and context) or other relevant key elements used to conceptualize the review questions and/or objectives.	2-3
METHODS			
Protocol and registration	5	Indicate whether a review protocol exists; state if and where it can be accessed (e.g., a Web address); and if available, provide registration information, including the registration number.	Not applicable (this is a protocol)
Eligibility criteria	6	Specify characteristics of the sources of evidence used as	3-6

		eligibility criteria (e.g., years considered, language, and publication status), and provide a rationale.	
Information sources*	7	Describe all information sources in the search (e.g., databases with dates of coverage and contact with authors to identify additional sources), as well as the date the most recent search was executed.	6-7
Search	8	Present the full electronic search strategy for at least 1 database, including any limits used, such that it could be repeated.	6-7
Selection of sources of evidence†	9	State the process for selecting sources of evidence (i.e., screening and eligibility) included in the scoping review.	7-8
Data charting process‡	10	Describe the methods of charting data from the included sources of evidence (e.g., calibrated forms or forms that have been tested by the team before their use, and whether data charting was done independently or in duplicate) and any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators.	11-14
Data items	11	List and define all variables for which data were sought and any assumptions and simplifications made.	8-11
Critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence§	12	If done, provide a rationale for conducting a critical appraisal of included sources of evidence; describe the methods used and how this information was used in any data synthesis (if appropriate).	11
Synthesis of results	13	Describe the methods of handling and summarizing the data that were charted.	11-14
RESULTS			

-	14-18	-	Not applicable – this is a protocol
DISCUSSION			
-	19-21	-	Not applicable – this is a protocol
FUNDING			
Funding	22	Describe sources of funding for the included sources of evidence, as well as sources of funding for the scoping review. Describe the role of the funders of the scoping review.	15

JB1 = Joanna Briggs Institute; PRISMA-ScR = Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews.

* Where *sources of evidence* (see second footnote) are compiled from, such as bibliographic databases, social media platforms, and Web sites.

† A more inclusive/heterogeneous term used to account for the different types of evidence or data sources (e.g., quantitative and/or qualitative research, expert opinion, and policy documents) that may be eligible in a scoping review as opposed to only studies. This is not to be confused with *information sources* (see first footnote).

‡ The frameworks by Arksey and O'Malley (6) and Levac and colleagues (7) and the JB1 guidance (4, 5) refer to the process of data extraction in a scoping review as data charting.

§ The process of systematically examining research evidence to assess its validity, results, and relevance before using it to inform a decision. This term is used for items 12 and 19 instead of "risk of bias" (which is more applicable to systematic reviews of interventions) to include and acknowledge the various sources of evidence that may be used in a scoping review (e.g., quantitative and/or qualitative research, expert opinion, and policy document).

<http://annals.org/aim/fullarticle/2700389/prisma-extension-scoping-reviews-prisma-scr-checklist-explanation>